

Modeling and simulation of unstirred dead end ultrafiltration of macromolecules[†]

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Abstract : A mass transfer model based on unsteady state component balance over the concentration boundary layer has been developed in the present study. The model uses semi-infinite consideration in order to solve the governing partial differential equation by Laplace transform that gives an analytical expression for the concentration profile. During the solution procedure, pseudo steady state assumption has been used, as a consequence of which permeate flux and membrane surface concentration have been taken constant over any small time interval. Once the expression for concentration profile is known, a time evolution loop has been developed to simulate the permeate flux, membrane surface concentration and permeate concentration under specified operating conditions of transmembrane pressure drop and bulk concentration. The prediction of the proposed model was found to be in good agreement with experimental results obtained during unstirred dead end ultrafiltration of polyethylene glycol (of average molecular weight 6000) solution using a cellulose acetate membrane of 5000 Da molecular weight cut-off.

Keywords : Ultrafiltration, permeate flux, membrane, simulation.

Introduction

Ultrafiltration (UF) is primarily a size exclusion based pressure driven membrane separation technique. Generally its operating pressure varies in the range of 1–10 bar, though in some cases 20–25 bar has been reported. UF membranes typically are capable of retaining species typically in the molecular weight range of 300–500000 Da. During the last few decades UF has been considered as a promising technology to solve different types of separation problems in various industries like food processing, pharmaceuticals, pulp and paper, paints, etc.

In UF, the solute species generally accumulates on the membrane surface because of their rejection by the membrane. As a result a concentration gradient sets in spanning itself from membrane surface to the bulk. This phenomenon is known as “concentration polarization”. Due to the increased resistance of polarized layer volume flux decreases with time. Moreover, any attempt to in-

crease the flux by increasing pressure causes severe increase in concentration polarization, thus giving a little increase in the permeate flux as compared to the increased pressure. Thus, a better understanding of the separation mechanism during ultrafiltration is necessary in order to eliminate the effects of concentration polarization. Wide variations of module design are now available in industry¹; usually a cross flow type module is preferred for industrial use. But for laboratory purpose, a flat disc membrane is commonly used either in continuous or in batch mode, with or without stirring facility. Though in stirred cell the stabilized flux is higher than that in unstirred cell under identical operating conditions, unstirred cell is preferred in most of the small scale operations as the stirred module requires elaborate sealing accessories surrounding the stirrer port involving higher cost.

Although different rigorous predictive models exist, UF technology still continues to centre on models based

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

on film theory. Shen and Probstein² first attempted the solution of unstirred batch ultrafiltration of macromolecular solutions. Terrin and Doshi³ reported a complete solution of unstirred cell using an integral method of analysis. The same process was also studied by Chudacek and Fane⁴ in which they have used the modified filtration theory and Kozeny-Carmann relationship to predict the permeate flux and permeate side concentration. Effects of diffusion and osmosis on flux decline in batch UF cell was studied by Danes *et al.*⁵. Bhattacharjee and Bhattacharya⁶ developed an iterative technique in order to evaluate the permeate flux as well as the membrane surface concentration for the analysis of unstirred cell ultrafiltration of kraft black liquor. Later Ghose *et al.*⁷ proposed a numerical simulation scheme for the same device based on boundary layer concept. Artificial neural network technique was used by Rai *et al.*⁸ for the performance analysis of unstirred batch ultrafiltration of synthetic fruit juice, whereas Magueijo *et al.*⁹ used surface force approach to model a lysozyme ultrafiltration. Recently Xiarchos *et al.*¹⁰ have used the response surface methodology to model the performance of micelle enhanced ultrafiltration and on the other hand the use of Fuzzy Interface System for milk ultrafiltration has been reported by Sargolzai *et al.*¹¹.

The present work has been undertaken in an attempt to develop an analytical model of unstirred batch ultrafiltration involving boundary layer mass transfer along with Flory-Huggins theory of polymer solution and irreversible thermodynamics fitting 16 sets of experimental data for unstirred batch cell during ultrafiltration of polyethylene glycol (PEG-6000, as the average molecular weight of the sample was 6000) by cellulose acetate membrane under unsteady state conditions. The objective of the study was to predict the time evolution of the three characteristic process variables, namely the permeate flux, membrane surface concentration and permeate concentration by a simple iterative technique so that it can be readily accepted in a standard control system design or may be treated as an entry point of a more accurate mathematical model.

Model formulation

Development of component balance equation :

Fig. 1 shows the flux condition inside a dead end unstirred module. The unsteady state component balance (of solute) over a differential element of thickness Δz

Fig. 1. Mass balance diagram inside the unstirred batch cell ultrafiltration module (not in scale).

lying at a distance z from the membrane surface yields the following partial differential equation,

$$J(c|_{z+\Delta z} - c|_z) + \left(D \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} \Big|_{z+\Delta z} - D \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} \Big|_z \right) = \Delta z \frac{\partial c}{\partial t}$$

$$\Rightarrow J \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} + D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial z^2} = \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

The equation assumes constant diffusivity and pseudo steady permeate flux. Considering the physical situation inside the unstirred cell, the applicable initial and boundary conditions of eq. (1) are formulated as,

- (i) at $t = 0$, $c = c_0$ for all z
- (ii) at $z = 0$, $c = c_m$ for $t > 0$
- (iii) as $z \rightarrow \infty$, $c = c_0$ for all $t > 0$

Introducing the following dimensionless quantities :

$\hat{c} = \frac{c}{c_0}$, $\hat{z} = \frac{z}{H}$ and $\hat{t} = \frac{Dt}{H^2}$, eq. (1) can be transformed into a dimensionless form as,

$$\frac{\partial \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{t}} = \frac{\partial^2 \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{z}^2} + \kappa \frac{\partial \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{z}} \quad (2)$$

where $\kappa = \frac{JH}{D}$ and H is the level of feed inside the cell as shown in Fig. 1. In terms of introduced dimensionless parameters the initial and the boundary conditions become,

- (i) at $\hat{t} = 0$, $\hat{c} = 1$ for all \hat{z}
- (ii) at $\hat{z} = 0$, $\hat{c} = \frac{c_m}{c_0}$ for $\hat{t} > 0$
- (iii) as $\hat{z} \rightarrow \infty$, $\hat{c} = 1$ for all $\hat{t} > 0$

Eq. (2) can be solved analytically via Laplace transform, followed by evaluation of complementary function and particular integral, therefrom coefficient evaluation by using initial and boundary conditions to obtain the complete solution in Laplace domain, which can be mapped again onto the time domain by taking the inverse Laplace transform resulting,

$$\hat{c}(\hat{z}, \hat{t}) = \frac{c_m - 1}{c_0} \left[\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{\hat{z}}{2\sqrt{\hat{t}}} + \frac{\kappa\sqrt{\hat{t}}}{2} \right) + \exp(-\kappa\hat{z}) \cdot \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{\hat{z}}{2\sqrt{\hat{t}}} + \frac{\kappa\sqrt{\hat{t}}}{2} \right) \right] + 1 \quad (3)$$

The detailed solution procedure of eq. (2) is given in Appendix A. From eq. (3) the instantaneous concentration profile can be evaluated using current values of the membrane surface concentration and permeate flux, which are as yet unknown.

Calculation of membrane surface concentration :

According to osmotic pressure model¹² transmembrane pressure drop (ΔP) is related to permeate flux as,

$$J = \frac{\Delta P - \sigma \Delta \pi}{\mu R_m} \quad (4)$$

where R_m is the membrane hydraulic resistance, μ is the viscosity of the feed solution, σ is the reflection coefficient and $\Delta \pi$ is the osmotic pressure differential i.e. $\Delta \pi = \pi_m - \pi_p$ (π_m and π_p are the osmotic pressures on the feed and permeate side respectively). From Flory-Huggins theory osmotic pressure can be related to solute concentration (for a macromolecular solute) as,

$$\pi = -\frac{RT}{V_w} \left[\ln \left(1 - \frac{c}{\rho_{pol}} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \right) \frac{c}{\rho_{pol}} + \chi \left(\frac{c}{\rho_{pol}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (5)$$

where n is the number of repeat units, ρ_{pol} is the density of the solute, V_w is the molar volume of the solvent, χ is the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter. Evaluating π_m and π_p by eq. (5) followed by substitution of osmotic pressure differential in eq. (4), the equation can be transformed to a non linear algebraic equation, which is as follows,

$$J - \frac{\sigma RT \left[\ln \left(\frac{\rho_{pol} - c_m}{\rho_{pol} - c_p} \right) + \frac{c_m - c_p}{\rho_{pol}} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \right) + \chi \cdot \frac{c_m - c_p}{\rho_{pol}} \right\} \right]}{\mu R_m} = 0 \quad (6)$$

It is to be noted that the viscosity of PEG-6000 solution in water is a strong function of corresponding solute concentration and can be related to the solute concentration¹³ as,

$$\mu = (0.85 + 0.1446 c' + 2.734 \times 10^{-4} c'^2 - 4.276 \times 10^{-6} c'^3 + 2.84 \times 10^{-8} c'^4) / 10^3 \quad (7)$$

where c' is in g cm^{-3} . The values of R , T and V_w to be used in the simulation program are $R = 8314 \text{ Pa.m}^3 \text{ kmol}^{-1} \text{ .K}$, $T = 303.15 \text{ K}$ and $V_w = 0.001 \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$. Incorporating eq. (7) in eq. (6) with concentration of the solute replaced by membrane surface concentration (c_m) the first algebraic equation of the unstirred dead end UF module becomes,

$$J - \frac{\sigma RT \left[\ln \left(\frac{\rho_{pol} - c_m}{\rho_{pol} - c_p} \right) + \frac{c_m - c_p}{\rho_{pol}} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \right) + \chi \cdot \frac{c_m - c_p}{\rho_{pol}} \right\} \right]}{(0.85 + 0.1446 \times 10^3 c_m + 2.734 \times 10^{-1} c_m^2 - 4.276 \times 10^{-3} c_m^3 + 2.84 \times 10^{-5} c_m^4) \times 10^{-3} R_m} = 0 \quad (8)$$

By an alternative approach via irreversible thermodynamics permeate flux J can also be expressed as a function of c_m and c_p as¹⁴,

$$1 - \frac{c_p}{c_m} = \frac{\sigma(1-F)}{1-\sigma F} \quad (9)$$

where $F = \exp\left\{\frac{-(1-\sigma)J}{P_m}\right\}$, P_m is the solute permeability

through the membrane. Eqs. (8) and (9) constitutes two simultaneous algebraic equations of three main process variables, namely J , c_m and c_p in time implicit form. In order to design an unsteady state simulation scheme of the unstirred cell additionally a time explicit relation of the form $\varphi(c_m, c_p, J, t) = 0$ is necessary.

Formulation of $\varphi(c_m, c_p, J, t) = 0$:

Assuming a pseudo steady membrane surface concentration the component balance equation at the membrane surface can be developed as,

$$J = -\frac{D}{c_m - c_p} \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} \quad (10)$$

Now, $\frac{\partial c}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} = \frac{c_0}{H} \frac{\partial \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{z}} \Big|_{z=0}$. On simplification using eqs. (3) and (10) the following time explicit relation between J , c_m and c_p is as obtained,

$$J = \frac{D}{c_m - c_p} \frac{c_0}{H} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{c_m}{c_0}}{2} \right) \left[\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi \hat{t}}} \exp\left(-\frac{\kappa^2 \hat{t}}{4}\right) + \kappa \left\{ 1 + \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{\kappa \sqrt{\hat{t}}}{2}\right) \right\} \right] \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) is a non linear algebraic equation with J , c_m and c_p as the dependent and \hat{t} as the independent variable of the system. At any specific time instant eq. (11) can be converted to a simple algebraic equation of J , c_m and c_p upon substitution of \hat{t} that corresponds to given time (t). Hence eq. (11) along with eqs. (8) and (9) constitutes a set of three simultaneous algebraic equations for the three main process variables namely J , c_m and c_p , where from the variables can be solved by using a suitable numerical

technique. In addition to that the existing concentration profile can also be generated by using eq. (3) as it is.

Evaluation of necessary process parameters

For the experimental validation of the proposed model the accurate evaluation of different process parameters namely, D , σ , P_m , R_m , χ , ρ_{pol} , n , H and V_w are necessary.

Firstly the solute diffusivity can be expressed as a function of molecular weight of the same (M) following a standard empirical equation as given below¹⁵,

$$D = 2.74 \times 10^{-9} \cdot \frac{1}{M_{pol}^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (12)$$

where D is expressed in $m^2 s^{-1}$. For PEG sample used in the present study the average molecular weight was 6000 and according to eq. (10) the diffusivity becomes $1.51 \times 10^{-10} m^2 s^{-1}$. Reflection coefficient (σ) and permeability (P_m) was determined by the well known method proposed by Nakao and Kimura¹⁴ and their numerical values for the present system are 0.98 and $1.83 \times 10^{-6} m s^{-1}$ respectively. The membrane hydraulic resistance was determined by making a series of water runs in the UF cell, after allowing initial compaction. The membrane hydraulic resistance (R_m) was calculated for all the experiments after allowing for initial compaction, by inducing the membrane to a higher pressure than the experimental range. The average of all the values obtained from different water runs was considered as the acceptable value and it was found to be $1.96 \times 10^{13} m^{-1}$. The value of χ i.e. the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter was reported in literature¹³ to be 0.45 under the operating temperature of 300 K for PEG/water system. n and ρ_{pol} values for the PEG sample was found to be 137 (as the average molecular weight of the polymeric solute, $M_{pol} = 6000$ and molecular weight of the repeat unit, $M_{rep} = 44$, hence

$$n = \frac{M_{pol}}{M_{rep}} = 137 \text{ and } 1125 \text{ kg } m^{-3}.$$

As the feed was supplied to the UF cell by a metering pump and the pressure inside the cell was adjusted by piston movement screw, the liquid level inside the cell (H) must be same as the ratio of useful internal volume to the internal cross sectional area, accordingly the liquid level was calculated to be 0.132 m. Which remains constant throughout an experimental run as the optimum feed circulation system compensates the loss of material due to permeate flux.

Simulation algorithm

Details of the simulation algorithm are shown in Fig. 2. It becomes evident from the figure that different parameters of the system are to be specified correctly as the input data along with the time up to which simulation is to be conducted. The flow chart contains only one time progression loop for unsteady state simulation of three

major process variables namely the permeate flux, membrane surface concentration and permeate concentration i.e. J , c_m and c_p . For solving three simultaneous algebraic equations at any specific time instant (eqs. (8), (9) and (11)) Newton-Raphson method with a tolerance of 10^{-8} for permeate flux, 10^{-2} for membrane surface concentration and 10^{-3} for permeate concentration have been used

Fig. 2. Algorithm for the simulation of permeate flux, membrane surface concentration, permeate concentration and volume fraction profile.

in the present study. Once the current values of J , c_m and c_p are known, the feed side solute concentration profile $\{c(z,t), z \in [0, H]\}$ can be determined using eq. (3) upon

substitution of $c_m(t)$, $\hat{t}\left(\frac{Dt}{H^2}\right)$, $\kappa\left(\frac{J(t)H}{D}\right)$ and c_0 for dif-

ferent $\hat{z}\left(=\frac{z}{H}\right)$ starting from $\hat{z} = 0$ (membrane surface)

up to $\hat{z} = 1$ (i.e. $z = H$, which corresponds to the feed side level in the UF cell).

Experimental

Materials :

Polyethylene glycol (PEG-6000, AR grade) in the average molecular weight range 6000 was obtained from Fluka, England. Moist 'Spectra-Por C5' cellulose acetate complex membrane (asymmetric, cut-off size : 5000) was obtained from Spectrum Medical Industries (USA). The membranes are usable in the pH range 2–10; they are hydrophilic and resistant to temperature up to 90 °C.

Apparatus :

An unstirred batch UF cell was developed and fabricated with the following specifications : material of construction, SS-316; useful volume, 600 cm³; residual volume, nil; UF cell diameter, 7.6 cm; maximum testing pressure, 3.5 × 10⁶ Pa.

Analysis :

Solution concentrations were measured with a refractometer (model P70, Warsaw, Poland). The density and viscosity were determined by solution concentration at 30 °C.

Design of experiment :

In order to validate the model with respect to permeate flux, experiments were designed in such a way so that the effect of two independent variables, namely bulk concentration (18, 30, 40 and 60 kg/m³) and transmembrane pressure drop (587.7, 490.5, 392.4 and 294.3 kPa) could be investigated. Any one of the variables was kept constant while the other was varied in order to get the actual nature of dependence. As there were two parameters and four distinct values for each of the parameters, 16 sets of experimental data were necessary in order to get a clear trend of permeate flux with the change of these parameters.

Procedure :

The membrane was placed on a disk shaped porous

support, fitted with a tube through which permeate flows out through the cell, and the cell was assembled. In order to overcome compaction effect of membrane, the cell was subjected to distilled water for at least 2 h at 900 kPa, which was higher than the highest operational pressure. After getting constant water flux membrane hydraulic resistance (R_m) was determined. This was followed by actual experimental run. A metering pump was used to charge the feed solution into the cell. To determine current value of volume flux, 5 cm³ of permeate was collected in a measuring cylinder and time for this collection was recorded. Flux values were recorded every 5 min. A particular run was continued until two successive flux reading were equal.

Once the run was over, the membrane was thoroughly cleaned with distilled water at least for 2 h to remove any deposition. The water flux then again checked to detect any variation in the membrane hydraulic resistance. The same procedure was repeated for each set of operating condition.

Results and discussion

Once the membrane has been compacted, several water runs were taken at different pressure as mentioned before to determine the hydraulic resistance of the membrane. Out of generated sets of experimental data 8 sets were used for the purpose of comparison with the unsteady state trend predicted by the proposed model whereas for the steady state comparison all the 16 sets of corresponding permeate flux data have been used.

Fig. 3 shows the variations of permeate flux with respect to time for four different transmembrane pressure drops with fixed bulk concentration ($c_0 = 18$ kg/m³). On an average the permeate flux was noticed to be decreasing by 85–90% as the system attains its corresponding steady state starting from $t = 0$. The figure also indicates a decreasing trend of permeate flux (both in steady as well as in unsteady state) with decreasing pressure while keeping the bulk concentration unchanged. A closer investigation reveals that as the transmembrane pressure drop was increased from 294.3 to 587.7 kPa the steady state permeate flux was increasing by 290%, whereas for the same change of pressure only 97% increase was no-

Fig. 3. Variation of experimental and predicted flux as a function of time (s) at different transmembrane pressure, but at constant bulk concentration ($c_0 = 18 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

ted initially ($t = 0$). On the other hand Fig. 4 represents the variation of flux profile for different bulk con-

informative the variation of steady state flux with transmembrane pressure drop for different bulk concentra-

Fig. 4. Variation of experimental and predicted flux as a function of time (s) at different bulk concentration, but at constant transmembrane pressure ($\Delta P = 294.3 \text{ kPa}$).

centrations at a fixed transmembrane pressure drop of 294.3 kPa. It becomes evident from the figure that though the initial permeate flux varies significantly with bulk concentration the corresponding steady state values are practically same because of the increasing influence of concentration polarization with time. In order to be more

tions is shown in Fig. 5. The figure shows a stabilizing trend of the steady flux with increasing pressure. The maximum absolute deviation between the model prediction and experimental result of steady as well as unsteady state permeate flux was noticed to be well within 6.5%. Probably the source of error is rooted in the pseudo steady

Fig. 5. Variation of steady state flux with transmembrane pressure for different bulk concentrations.

state assumption of permeate flux, but at the same time it is to be considered that without the stated assumption it was impossible to solve the concentration profile analytically and the resulting model would have been much more complex from the standpoint of its mathematical struc-

ture. Similar to the unsteady state flux profile and the variation of steady state flux with respect to pressure, predicted values of permeate concentration (c_p) were also compared with that of experimental data for different transmembrane pressure drop as shown in Fig. 6. Permeate

Fig. 6. Variation of experimental and predicted permeate concentration as a function of time (s) at different transmembrane pressure but at constant bulk concentration ($c_0 = 18 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

concentration is one of the very important process variables in order to get an idea about the general performance characteristics of any standard dead end module. Moreover knowing the membrane surface concentration in addition to permeate concentration, "real" rejection

$\left(1 - \frac{c_m}{c_p}\right)$ can be predicted. It was observed that with the

increase in pressure permeate concentration increases, which is very evident from the fact that the excluded volume of the PEG chains might get reduced due to the increased pressure, thus the chains may reptate through the pores of the membrane leading to a high permeate side concentration. Predicted result matches well with the experimental data (maximum absolute deviation is within 4%), showing the applicability of the proposed model in

through a maxima, as depicted in the inset. The solute flux increases with the increase of transmembrane pressure drop, as expected because the increased pressure increases the solvent flow out through the cell and by reducing the excluded volume of the polymer species it also increases the solute permeation through the membrane.

Fig. 7 shows the formation of concentration profile with respect to time for a fixed transmembrane pressure drop (294.3 kPa) and bulk concentration (18 kg/m³). The initial flat concentration grows over time. The effective thickness of the concentration boundary layer (the distance from the membrane surface at which $\frac{\partial c}{\partial z} = 0$) increases with time marking increased effects of concentration polarization.

Fig. 7. Development of concentration profile and adsorbed free segment's statistical weight as a function of time (s) at fixed transmembrane pressure ($\Delta P = 294.3$ kPa) and bulk concentration ($c_0 = 18$ kg/m³).

predicting permeate concentration and hence the rejection. To be more informative the variations of solute flux (product of permeate flux and permeate side concentration, Jc_p) with time (both the experimental as well as predicted by the model) for four different transmembrane pressure drops but at fixed bulk concentration is shown as an inset of Fig. 6. As the permeate flux decreases (Fig. 2) and the permeate concentration increases with time (Fig. 6), therefore the variation of solute flux must go

The variation of membrane surface concentration with time for different transmembrane pressure drop is shown in Fig. 8. Initially a sharp increase in c_m can be readily observed over a short time (within first 5 min) thereafter the surface concentration finally approaches the corresponding steady state value at which $\Delta\pi = \Delta\pi_{\max}$ and the effective driving force reaches its minima leading to the lowest possible value of the permeate flux i.e. the steady state value under the specified operating conditions.

Fig. 8. Variation of membrane surface concentration with time at different transmembrane pressures but at fixed bulk concentration ($c_0 = 18 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

In Fig. 9, the growth of membrane surface concentration with respect to time has been plotted as a function of bulk concentration. The figure shows that the membrane surface concentration over the entire unsteady state re-

force practically independent of bulk concentration for a given transmembrane pressure drop.

Conclusion :

A model based on the solution of partial differential

Fig. 9. Variation of membrane surface concentration with time at different bulk concentrations but at fixed transmembrane pressure ($\Delta P = 294.3 \text{ kPa}$).

gime is practically independent of bulk concentration, though a marginally higher value is expected for a higher bulk concentration. Actually in a typical unstirred cell the surface concentration tends to a limiting value at which ΔP is close to $\Delta \pi$. This will happen if the solute does not precipitate to form 'gel' over the membrane surface, which is true for PEG-6000. So here the process of ultrafiltration is totally osmotic pressure controlled, with driving

equation arising from fundamental component balance equation for an unstirred dead end ultrafiltration module has been attempted in this study. In addition to the permeate flux the unsteady state membrane surface and permeate concentrations have also been evaluated through osmotic pressure model coupled with the Flory-Huggins theory and flux-rejection relationship resulting from irreversible thermodynamics. Finally a simulation scheme

was developed to generate the time evolution of system in terms of flux, surface concentration and permeate concentration under a specified set of operating conditions. The model prerequisite is the accurate estimation of three system parameters, i.e. R_m , P_m and σ , in this point of view the model can be termed as a four parameter model of a standard unstirred ultrafiltration cell. The proposed model was validated with experimental data for PEG-6000 solution treated with cellulose acetate membrane in an unstirred batch cell. The average of the absolute deviation was found to be 5.2% for the simulation of permeate flux and 3.1% for the permeate concentration demonstrating that the model could be used to accurately simulate the flux and permeate concentration during an unstirred dead end ultrafiltration of macromolecules.

Appendix A : Solution procedure of eq. (2)

The equation to be solved : $\frac{\partial \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{t}} = \frac{\partial^2 \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{z}^2} + \kappa \frac{\partial \hat{c}}{\partial \hat{z}}$

The initial and boundary conditions are

(i) at $\hat{t} = 0$, $\hat{c} = 1$ for all \hat{z}

(ii) at $\hat{z} = 0$, $\hat{c} = \frac{c_m}{c_0}$ for $\hat{t} > 0$

(iii) as $\hat{z} \rightarrow \infty$, $\hat{c} = 1$ for all $\hat{t} > 0$

Taking Laplace transform of eq. (2) and applying boundary condition (i)

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{\hat{c}}(\hat{z}, s)}{d\hat{z}^2} + \kappa \frac{d\bar{\hat{c}}}{d\hat{z}} - s\bar{\hat{c}} = -1 \quad (A1)$$

The eq. (A1) can be solved by solving for CF and PI individually as :

(I) Complementary Function :

$$CF : \bar{\hat{c}}(\hat{z}, s) = C_1 e^{m_1 \hat{z}} + C_2 e^{m_2 \hat{z}}$$

where $m_1, m_2 = \frac{-\kappa \pm \sqrt{\kappa^2 + 4s}}{2}$ C_1, C_2 are arbitrary constants.

(II) Particular Integral :

$$PI : \frac{1}{s}$$

The complete solution in Laplace domain can be written as :

$$\bar{\hat{c}}(\hat{z}, s) = C_1 e^{m_1 \hat{z}} + C_2 e^{m_2 \hat{z}} + \frac{1}{s} \quad (A2)$$

Applying boundary conditions (ii) and (iii) the solution becomes :

$$\bar{\hat{c}}(\hat{z}, s) = \left(\frac{c_m - 1}{c_0} \right) \exp\left(\frac{-\kappa - \sqrt{\kappa^2 + 4s}}{2} \hat{z} \right) + \frac{1}{s} \quad (A3)$$

Taking the inverse Laplace transform using shifting theorem and Laplace transform tables the complete solution of eq. (2) in time domain is as obtained :

$$\hat{c}(\hat{z}, t) = \frac{c_m - 1}{2} \left[\operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{\hat{z}}{2\sqrt{\hat{t}}} + \frac{\kappa\sqrt{\hat{t}}}{2} \right) + \exp(-\kappa\hat{z}) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{\hat{z}}{2\sqrt{\hat{t}}} - \frac{\kappa\sqrt{\hat{t}}}{2} \right) \right] + 1$$

Notations :

- c Solute concentration (kg m^{-3})
- c_m Solute concentration at membrane surface (kg m^{-3})
- c_p Solute concentration in the permeate (kg m^{-3})
- c_0 Bulk solute concentration (kg m^{-3})
- \hat{c} Dimensionless concentration = $\frac{c}{c_0}$
- C_1, C_2 Arbitrary constants defined in Appendix A
- D Solute diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
- F Parameter defined in eq. (7)
- H Liquid level inside the UF cell (m)
- J Permeate flux ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
- m_1, m_2 Roots of the auxiliary equation defined in Appendix A
- M_{pol} Average molecular weight of polymer (kg kmol^{-1})
- M_{rep} Molecular weight of repeat unit (kg kmol^{-1})
- n Average number of repeat units in a polymer chain
- ΔP Transmembrane pressure drop (kPa)
- P_m Solute permeability (ms^{-1})
- PEG Polyethylene glycol
- R Gas constant ($=8314 \text{ Pa.m}^3.\text{kmol}^{-1}$)

R_m	Membrane hydraulic resistance (m^{-1})
S	Independent variable of Laplace domain
t	Time (s)
\hat{t}	Dimensionless time $\left(= \frac{Dt}{H^2} \right)$
T	Absolute temperature (K)
UF	Ultrafiltration
V_w	Specific molar volume of the solvent ($m^3 \text{ kmol}^{-1}$)
z	Axial distance from membrane surface (m)
\hat{z}	Dimensionless distance $\left(= \frac{z}{H} \right)$
ρ_{pol}	Density of polymer (kg m^{-3})
π	Osmotic pressure (kPa)
$\Delta\pi$	Osmotic pressure differential (kPa)
σ	Reflection coefficient (dimensionless)
χ	Flory-Huggins interaction parameter

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